

Constrained Network Slicing Games: Achieving service guarantees and network efficiency

Jiaxiao Zheng*, Albert Banchs[†], Gustavo de Veciana*,

*The University of Texas at Austin, TX [†]University Carlos III of Madrid & IMDEA Networks Institute, Spain

Abstract—Network slicing is a key capability for next generation mobile networks. It enables infrastructure providers to cost effectively customize logical networks over a shared infrastructure. A critical component of network slicing is resource allocation, which needs to ensure that slices receive the resources needed to support their services while optimizing network efficiency. In this paper, we propose a novel approach to slice-based resource allocation named *Guaranteed seRvice Efficient nETwork slicing* (GREET). The underlying concept is to set up a *constrained* resource allocation game, where (i) slices unilaterally optimize their allocations to best meet their (dynamic) customer loads, while (ii) constraints are imposed to guarantee that, if they wish so, slices receive a pre-agreed share of the network resources. The resulting game is a variation of the well-known Fisher market, where slices are provided a budget to contend for network resources (as in a traditional Fisher market), but (unlike a Fisher market) prices are constrained for some resources to ensure that the pre-agreed guarantees are met for each slice. In this way, GREET combines the advantages of a share-based approach (high efficiency by flexible sharing) and reservation-based ones (which provide guarantees by assigning a fixed amount of resources). We characterize the Nash equilibrium, best response dynamics, and propose a practical slice strategy with provable convergence properties. Extensive simulations exhibit substantial improvements over network slicing state-of-the-art benchmarks.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is consensus among the relevant industry and standardization communities that a key element in future mobile networks is *network slicing*. This technology allows the network infrastructure to be “sliced” into logical networks, which are operated by different entities and may be tailored to support specific mobile services. This provides a basis for efficient infrastructure sharing among diverse entities, such as mobile network operators relying on a common infrastructure managed by an infrastructure provider, or new players that use a *network slice* to run their business (e.g., an automobile manufacturer providing advanced vehicular services, or a city hall providing smart city services). In the literature, the term *tenant* is often used to refer to the owner of a network slice.

A network slice is a collection of resources and functions that are orchestrated to support a specific service. This includes software modules running at different locations as well

The work of J. Zheng and G. de Veciana was supported in part NSF Award CNS-1910112. Meanwhile, part of the work was conducted during a visit of A. Banchs at the University of Texas at Austin funded by a Salvador de Madariaga grant of the Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture, and Sports. The work of A. Banchs was also supported in part by the European Union’s Horizon-JU-SNS-2022 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095871 (TrialsNet) and by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union-NextGenerationEU through the UNICO 5G I+D 6G-CLARION project.

as the nodes’ computational resources, and communication resources in the backhaul and radio network. By tailoring the orchestration of resources and functions of each slice according to the slice’s needs, network slicing enables tenants to share the same physical infrastructure while customizing the network operation according to their market segment’s characteristics and requirements.

One of the key components underlying network slicing is the framework for *resource allocation*: we need to decide how to assign the underlying infrastructure resources to each slice at each point in time. When taking such decisions, two major objectives are pursued: (i) meeting the tenants’ needs specified by slice-based Service Level Agreements (SLAs), and (ii) realizing efficient infrastructure sharing by maximizing the overall level of satisfaction across all slices. Recently, several efforts have been devoted to this problem. Two different types of approaches have emerged in the literature:

Reservation-based schemes [1]–[8] where a tenant issues a reservation request with a certain periodicity or on demand. Each request involves a given allocation for each resource in the network (where a resource can be a base station, a cloud server or a transmission link).¹

Share-based schemes [10]–[14] where a tenant does not issue reservation requests for individual resources, but rather purchases a share of the whole network. This share is then mapped dynamically to different allocations of individual resources depending on the tenants’ needs at each point in time.

These approaches have advantages and disadvantages. Reservation-based schemes are in principle able to guarantee that a slice’s requirements are met, but to be efficient, require constant updating of the resource allocations to track changing user loads, capacities and/or demands. The overheads of doing so at a fine granularity can be substantial, including challenges with maintaining state consistency to enable admission control, modifying reservations and addressing handoffs. Indeed, these overheads are already deemed high for basic horizontal and/or vertical handoffs. As a result, resource allocations typically need to be done at a coarser granularity and slower time-scales, resulting in reduced overall efficiency and performance.

In contrast to the above, in share-based approaches a slice

¹Reservation-based schemes follow a similar QoS architectures as wired networks such as IntServ and DiffServ, see e.g., [9]. A key difference is that in a mobile slice setting one needs to account for user dynamics, including changes in their associations, across a pool of resources (e.g., set of wireless base stations).

is given a coarse-grained share of the network resources which combined with a fine-grained dynamic policy can track rapid changes in a slices' load distributions. Indeed, as these schemes do not involve explicit per resource reservation requests, they can more rapidly adapt allocations to the demand variations of network slices (see, e.g., [15]). Their main drawback, however, is that tenants do not have a guaranteed allocation at individual resources, and as a consequence they cannot ensure that slices' requirements will always be met.

Key contributions: In this paper, we propose a novel approach to resource allocation among network slices named *Guaranteed seRvice Efficient nETwork slicing* (GREET). GREET combines the advantages of the above two approaches while avoiding their drawbacks. The key idea is that a slice is guaranteed a given allocation at each individual resource, as long as the slice needs such an allocation, while the remaining resources are flexibly and efficiently shared. In this way, GREET is able to provide guarantees and thus meet the SLA requirement of each slice, and at the same time it provides a flexible sharing of resources across slices that leads to an overall optimal allocation. Our key contributions are as follows:

- We propose the *GREET slice-based resource allocation framework*, which relies on a *constrained* resource allocation game where slices can unilaterally optimize their allocations under some constraints which guarantee that slices are entitled to a pre-agreed amount of each individual network resource, specified in their SLAs (Section II).
- We analyze the resulting network slicing game when slices contend for resources to optimize their performance. We show that the game has a Nash Equilibrium (NE) but unfortunately the Best Response Dynamics (BRD) may not converge to this equilibrium (Section III).
- We propose a *GREET slice strategy for individual slices* that complements our resource allocation framework. The proposed strategy is simple and provides a good approximation to the slice's best response. We show conditions for convergence with the proposed strategy (Section IV).
- We perform a simulation-based evaluation confirming that GREET combines the best features of reservation-based and share-based approaches, providing service guarantees while maximizing the overall performance (Section V).

II. RESOURCE ALLOCATION APPROACH

In this section we introduce both the system model and the resource allocation framework proposed in this paper.

A. System model

We consider a set of resources \mathcal{B} shared by a set of slices \mathcal{V} , with cardinalities B and V , respectively. \mathcal{B} may denote a set of base stations as well as any other sharable resource type, e.g., servers providing compute resources. While our analysis can be applied to different resource types, in what follows we focus on radio resources and refer to $b \in \mathcal{B}$ as a base station.

We assume that each network slice supports a collection of mobile users, possibly with heterogeneous requirements,

each of which is associated with a single base station. The overall set of users on the network is denoted by \mathcal{U} , those supported by slice v are denoted by \mathcal{U}^v , those associated with base station b are denoted by \mathcal{U}_b , and we define $\mathcal{U}_b^v := \mathcal{U}_b \cap \mathcal{U}^v$. The set of active slices at base station b , corresponding to those that have at least one user at b , is denoted by \mathcal{V}_b (i.e., $|\mathcal{U}_b^v| > 0$ holds for $v \in \mathcal{V}_b$).

The goal in this paper is to develop a mechanism to allocate resources amongst slices. To that end, we let f_b^v denote the fraction of resources at base station b allocated to slice v . We adopt a generic formulation in which we assume infinitely divisible resources that can be applied to a variety of technologies. The specific resource notion will depend on the underlying technology; for instance, in OFDM resources refer to physical resource blocks, in FDM to bandwidth and in TDM to the fraction of time. Note that typical wireless technologies have a granularity on which fine grain resources are made, e.g., resource blocks, yet these are typically small relative to the overall frame, or are shared over time, whence the impact of rounding errors will be small.

The resources of a base station allocated to a slice are subdivided among the slice's users at the base stations, such that a user $u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v$ receives a fraction f_u of the resource, where $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} f_u = f_b^v$. With such an allocation, user u achieves a service rate $r_u = f_u \cdot c_u$, where c_u is defined as the average rate of the user per resource unit under current radio conditions. Note that c_u depends on the modulation and coding scheme selected for the user given the current radio conditions, which accounts for noise as well as the interference from the neighboring base stations. Following similar analyses in the literature (see, e.g., [16]–[18]), we shall assume that c_u is fixed for each user at a given time.²

The focus of this paper is on *slice-based resource allocation*: our problem is to decide which fraction of the overall resources we allocate to each slice (e.g., the number of resource blocks of each base station). In order to translate slice-based allocations to specific user-level allocations, the system will further need to decide (i) which specific resources (beyond the fraction of resources) will be assigned to each slice, and in turn, (ii) the assignment of slice resources to active users. This corresponds to a user-level scheduling problem which is not in the scope of this paper, but may impact the users' achievable rates c_u (this problem has been addressed, for instance, in [20]–[22]).

In line with standard network slicing frameworks [23], the approach studied in this paper can be flexibly combined with different algorithms for user-level allocations. The specific mechanism to assign resources to slices is the responsibility of the infrastructure provider, which may take into account, e.g., the latency requirements of the different slices. The sharing of the resources of a slice amongst its users is up to the slice, and different slices may run different scheduling algorithms

²Note that assuming constant c_u represents an abstraction of the underlying physical resources, which accounts for the various techniques employed at the physical layer, possibly including multi-user MIMO. After determining the desired allocation across slices and users, physical layer techniques such as multi-user MIMO are employed to optimize the resource usage while following the multi-slice sharing policy. For instance, [19] relies on average (coarse) estimates for the rates and orthogonality to make scheduling decisions and then uses multi-user MIMO physical layer to optimize transmissions for scheduled users.

depending on the requirements of their users. For instance, slices with throughput-driven services may opt for opportunistic schedulers [24]–[26] while other slices with latency requirements may opt for delay-sensitive schedulers [27]. Protocols and algorithms for QoS enforcement such as IntServ and DiffServ might also be adapted to realize slice-level allocations.

Depending on its type of traffic, a slice may require different allocations. For instance, an Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) slice with high reliability and/or low latency requirements may require a resource allocation much larger than its average load, to make sure sufficient resources are available and/or delays are low. By contrast, a slice with enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) traffic may not require guarantees at each individual base station, but may only need a certain average fraction of resources over time for its users.

B. GREET: Slice-based Resource Allocation

Below, we propose a slice-based resource allocation scheme that, on the one hand, ensures that each slice is guaranteed, *as needed*, a pre-agreed fraction of the resources at each individual base station, and, on the other hand, enables slices to contend for spare resources. Such a division into guaranteed resources and extra ones is in line with current sharing models for cloud computing [28]–[30]. In order to regulate the resources to which a network slice is entitled, as well as the competition for the ‘excess’ resources, we rely on the different types of *shares* defined below. Such shares are specified in the slices’ SLAs.

Definition 1. For each slice v , we define the following pre-agreed static shares of the network resources.

- 1) We let the **guaranteed share** s_b^v denote the fraction of b ’s resources guaranteed to slice v , which must satisfy $\sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} s_b^v \leq 1$ in order to avoid over-commitment.
- 2) We let e^v denote the **excess share** which slice v can use to contend for the spare network resources.
- 3) We let s^v denote the slice v ’s **overall share**, given by $s^v = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} s_b^v + e^v$.

After being provisioned a fraction of a network resource, each slice v has the option to sub-divide its share amongst its users. This can be done by designating a weight w_u for user $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$. We let $\mathbf{w}^v = (w_u, u \in \mathcal{U}^v)$ denote the weight allocation of slice v such that $\|\mathbf{w}^v\|_1 \leq s^v$. The set of feasible weight allocations is given by $\mathcal{W}^v := \{\mathbf{w}^v : \mathbf{w}^v \in \mathbb{R}_+^{|\mathcal{U}^v|} \text{ and } \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} w_u \leq s^v\}$. Then, we will have $l_b^v = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} w_u$ as the slice v ’s *aggregate weight* to base station b , which is determined by its user weight distribution and must satisfy that $\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} l_b^v \leq s^v$. We further let $l_b := \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}_b} l_b^v$ denote the *overall weight* on base station b and $l_b^{-v} := \sum_{v' \neq v} l_b^{v'}$ the overall weight excluding slice v . We define $\Delta_b^v := (l_b^v - s_b^v)_+$ as the *excess weight* at base station b of slice v . The proposed resource allocation mechanism works as follows.

Definition 2. (GREET slice-based resource allocation) We determine the fraction of each resource b allocated to slice v ,

$(f_b^v, v \in \mathcal{V}, b \in \mathcal{B})$, as follows. If $l_b \leq 1$, then

$$f_b^v = \frac{l_b^v}{l_b}, \quad (1)$$

and otherwise

$$f_b^v = \begin{cases} l_b^v, & l_b^v < s_b^v, \\ s_b^v + \frac{\Delta_b^v}{\sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \Delta_b^{v'}} \left(1 - \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \min(s_b^{v'}, l_b^{v'}) \right), & l_b^v \geq s_b^v. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The rationale underlying the above mechanism is as follows. If $l_b \leq 1$, then (1) ensures that each slice gets a fraction of resources f_b^v exceeding its aggregate weight l_b^v at resource b . If $l_b > 1$, then (2) ensures that a slice whose aggregate weight at b is less than its guaranteed share, i.e., $l_b^v \leq s_b^v$, receives exactly its aggregate weight, and a slice with an aggregate weight exceeding its guaranteed share, i.e., $l_b^v > s_b^v$, receives its guaranteed share s_b^v plus a fraction of the *extra resources* proportional to the excess weight Δ_b^v . The extra resources here correspond to those not allocated based on guaranteed shares. A slice can always choose a weight allocation such that the aggregate weight at resource b , l_b^v , exceeds its guaranteed share, s_b^v , and thus this ensures that, if it so wishes, a slice can always attain its guaranteed shares.

The above specifies the slice allocation per resource. Based on the w_u ’s, the slices then allocate base stations’ resources to users in proportion to their weights, i.e., $f_u = \frac{w_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} w_{u'}} f_b^v$, where f_u is the fraction of resources of base station b allocated to user $u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v$.

One can think of the above allocation in terms of market pricing schemes as follows. The share s^v can be understood the budget of player v and the aggregate weight l_b^v as the bid that this player places on resource b . Then, the case where $l_b \leq 1$ corresponds to the well-known Fisher market [31], where the price of the resource is set equal to the aggregate bids from slices, making allocations proportional to the slices’ bids. GREET deviates from this when $l_b \geq 1$ by modifying the ‘pricing’ as follows: for the first s_b^v bid of slice v on resource b , GREET sets the price to 1, to ensure that the slice budget suffices to buy the guaranteed resource shares. Beyond this, the remaining resources are priced higher, as driven by the corresponding slices’ excess bids.

In summary, the proposed slice-based resource allocation scheme is geared at ensuring a slice will, if it wishes, be able to get its guaranteed resource shares, s_b^v , but it also gives a slice the flexibility to contend for excess resources, by shifting portions of its overall share s^v (both from the guaranteed and excess shares) across the base stations, to better meet the current requirements of the slice’s users, by aligning the slice bids with the users’ traffic. Such a slice-based resource sharing model provides the benefit of protection guarantees as well as the flexibility to adapt to user demands.

III. NETWORK SLICING GAME ANALYSIS

Under the GREET resource allocation scheme, each slice must choose how to subdivide its overall share amongst its users. Then, the network decides how to allocate base station resources to slices. This can be viewed as a *network slicing game* where, depending on the choices of the other slices,

each slice chooses an allocation of aggregate weights to base stations that maximizes its utility. In this section, we study the behavior of this game.

A. Slice and Network Utilities

Note that the users' rate allocations, $(r_u : u \in \mathcal{U})$, can be expressed as a function of the slice's weight assignments across the network, $\mathbf{w} = (w_u : u \in \mathcal{U})$. Indeed, the weights determine the slice's resources at each base station, as well as the division of such resources across the slice's users within each base station. Accordingly, in the sequel we focus the game analysis on the weights and express the resulting user rates as $r_u(\mathbf{w})$.

We assume that each slice has a *private* utility function, denoted by U^v , that reflects the slice's preferences based on the needs of its users. We suppose the slice utility is simply a sum of its users individual utilities, U_u , i.e., $U^v(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} U_u(r_u(\mathbf{w}))$.

Following standard utility functions [32], [33], we assume that for some applications, a user $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$ may require a guaranteed rate γ_u , hereafter referred to as the user's *minimum rate requirement*. We model the utility functions for rates above the minimum requirement as follows:

$$U_u(r_u(\mathbf{w})) = \begin{cases} \phi_u F_u(r_u(\mathbf{w}) - \gamma_u), & r_u(\mathbf{w}) > \gamma_u, \\ -\infty & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $F_u(\cdot)$ is the utility function associated with the user, and ϕ_u reflects the *relative priority* that slice v wishes to give user u , with $\phi_u \geq 0$ and $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_u = 1$.

For $F_u(\cdot)$, we consider the following widely accepted family of functions, referred to as α -fair utility functions [34]:

$$F_u(x_u) = \begin{cases} \frac{(x_u)^{1-\alpha^v}}{(1-\alpha^v)}, & \alpha^v \neq 1 \\ \log(x_u), & \alpha^v = 1, \end{cases}$$

where the α^v parameter sets the level of concavity of the user utility functions, which in turn determines the underlying resource allocation criterion of the slice. Particularly relevant cases are $\alpha^v = 0$ (maximum sum), $\alpha^v = 1$ (proportional fairness), $\alpha^v = 2$ (minimum potential delay fairness) and $\alpha^v \rightarrow \infty$ (max-min fairness).

Note that the above utility is flexible in that it allows slice utilities to capture users with different types of traffic:

- *Elastic traffic* ($\gamma_u = 0$ and $\phi_u > 0$): users with no minimum rate requirements and a utility that increases with the allocated rate, possibly with different levels of concavity given by α^v .
- *Inelastic traffic* ($\gamma_u > 0$ and $\phi_u = 0$): users that have a minimum rate requirement but do not see any utility improvement beyond this rate.
- *Rate-adaptive traffic* ($\gamma_u > 0$ and $\phi_u > 0$): users with a minimum rate requirement which see a utility improvement if they receive an additional rate allocation above the minimum.

Following [10]–[13], we define the overall network utility as the sum of the individual slice utilities weighted by the

respective overall shares,³

$$U(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} s^v U^v(\mathbf{w}), \quad (4)$$

and the social optimal weight allocation \mathbf{w}^{so} as the allocation maximizing the overall utility $U(\mathbf{w})$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{w}^{\text{so}} = \underset{\mathbf{w} \geq 0}{\operatorname{argmax}} \{ U(\mathbf{w}) : \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} w_u \leq s^v, \forall v \in \mathcal{V} \} \quad (5)$$

The combination of the utility functions defined above with the resource allocation scheme defined in the previous section results in a game that we formalize in the next section. This game falls in a broader context of a substantial amount of work both in economics and networking. Broadly speaking the proposed mechanism can be informally described as one in which slices have 'shares', which can be viewed as budgets, that can be used to 'bid' for resources. As such, we are motivated by frameworks typically referred to as Fisher markets, where buyers can be modelled as either price-taking (see, e.g. [31]) or strategic (e.g. [35] and [12]). Other related work, particularly in the networking field has addressed settings where players do not have fixed budgets: [36] proposes a mechanism where resources are allocated in proportion to players bids and players are price-taking, [37] analyzes the efficiency losses of this mechanism and [38] devises a scalar-parameterized modification which is shown to be socially optimal for price-anticipating players. A more comprehensive discussion of past work can be found in [12]. The present work represents a departure from previous works in that it has been designed to ensure tenants allocations meet guarantees on individual resources while also allowing them to flexibly allocate pre-negotiated shares across resources.

B. Network Slicing Resource Allocation Game

Next we analyze the network slicing game resulting from the GREET resource allocation scheme and the above slice utility. We formally define the network slicing game as follows, where \mathbf{w}^v denotes slice v users' weights.

Definition 3. (Network slicing game) Suppose each slice v has access to the guaranteed shares and the aggregate weights of the other slices, i.e., $s_b^v, l_b^v, v' \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{v\}, b \in \mathcal{B}$. In the network slicing game, slice v chooses its own user weight allocation \mathbf{w}^v in its strategy space \mathcal{W}^v so as to maximize its utility, given that the network uses a GREET slice-based resource allocation. This choice is known as slice v 's Best Response (BR).

In the sequel we consider scenarios where the guaranteed shares suffice to meet the minimal rate requirements of all users. The underlying assumption is that a slice would provision a sufficient share and/or perform admission control so as to limit the number of users. We state this formally as follows:

Assumption 1. (Well dimensioned shares) The slices' guaranteed shares are said to be well dimensioned if they meet or exceed the minimum rate requirements of their users at each

³The slice utility is weighted by the overall shares to reflect the fact that tenants with higher overall shares should be favored – see [10]–[13] for a more detailed discussion.

base station. In particular, they are such that $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} f_u \leq s_b^v$ for all $v \in \mathcal{V}$ and $b \in \mathcal{B}$, where $f_u = \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u}$ is the minimum fraction of resource required by user u to meet its minimum rate requirement γ_u . When this assumption holds, we say that the shares of all slices are well dimensioned.

A more restrictive assumption is that each slice provision exactly the guaranteed share needed to meet its users' minimum rate requirements.

Assumption 2. (Perfectly dimensioned shares) The slices' guaranteed shares are said to be perfectly dimensioned if they are equal to minimum rate requirements of their users at each base station, i.e., $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} f_u = s_b^v$ for all $v \in \mathcal{V}$ and $b \in \mathcal{B}$. When this assumption holds, we say that the shares of all slices are perfectly dimensioned.

The above assumptions are typical in mobile networks, where in order to meet users' performance guarantees one will need to make admission control decisions that ensure that with high probability such conditions are met (see e.g. [13]). Still, due to channel variability and user mobility there will typically be a small probability that this conditions are not met. In this case our proposed mechanism will still work, i.e., the network does not "break", although some slices' users may not be able to meet their requirements and (as it will be seen later) some desirable properties may not hold.

The following lemma ensures that under Assumption 1 a slice's best response is given by the solution to a convex problem and meets the minimum rate requirements of all its users. Thus, as long as a slice's guaranteed shares are well dimensioned, the proposed scheme will meet the slice's users requirements.

Lemma 1. When Assumption 1 holds, a slice's Best Response under GREET-based resource allocation is the solution to a convex optimization problem, and the minimum rate requirements of all the slice's users will be satisfied.

To characterize the system, it is desirable to show that under a GREET-based resource allocation there exists a Nash Equilibrium (NE). It can be shown that, when the slices' shares are well dimensioned and weights are strictly positive (i.e., greater than a δ which can be arbitrarily small), then the necessary conditions of [39] for the existence of a NE hold. Note that the assumption on weights being strictly positive is a benign assumption which will typically hold for almost all utility functions. However, as shown in the lemma below, if the uniform constraint on weights being positive is not satisfied, then a NE may not exist.

Lemma 2. Suppose that Assumption 1 holds but we do constrain user weights to be uniformly strictly positive (i.e., for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ $w_u \geq \delta$ for some $\delta > 0$). Then, a NE may not exist under GREET-based resource allocation.

When a NE exists, it is natural to ask whether the dynamics of slices' unilateral best responses to each others weight allocations would lead to an equilibrium. Below, we consider Best Response Dynamics (BRD), where slices update their Best Response sequentially, one at a time, in a Round Robin manner. Ideally, we would like this process to converge after a sufficiently large number of rounds. However, the following

result shows that this need not be the case.

Theorem 1. Suppose that Assumption 1 holds and that we constrain user weights to be positive, i.e., for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ $w_u \geq \delta$ for some $\delta > 0$. Then, even though a NE exists, the Best Response Dynamics may not converge.⁴

Note that cooperative settings where for example slices might update their weights based on the gradient-based algorithm introduced in [39] to or use perhaps other updating policies based on for example reinforcement learning, may indeed converge. However in the slicing setting we envisage competitive scenarios where slices are selfish in optimizing their allocations.

The following two theorems further characterize the NE allocations of the network slicing game relative to the socially optimal resource allocation and in terms of envy, respectively.

Theorem 2. Consider a setting where all slices' users are elastic and have logarithmic utilities, i.e., $\alpha = 1$. Suppose also that a NE exists. Then, the overall utility associated with the socially optimal weight allocations \mathbf{w}^{so} versus that resulting from the NE of the network slicing game under GREET-based resource allocation, \mathbf{w}^{ne} , satisfy

$$U(\mathbf{w}^{so}) - U(\mathbf{w}^{ne}) \leq \log(e) \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} s^v$$

Furthermore, there exists a game instance for which this bound is tight.

Theorem 3. Consider a setting where slices satisfy Assumption 2 and a NE exists. Further, suppose that two slices v and \tilde{v} have the same guaranteed and excess shares and that slice v has users with logarithmic utilities, i.e., $\alpha^v = 1$. Let $\mathbf{r}^{ne,v}$ denote the rate allocations to slice v 's users under the NE. Suppose slice v and \tilde{v} exchange the overall allocations they get at the NE and let $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v$ denote the rate allocations to users of slice v maximizing slice v 's utility after such an exchange. Let us define the envy that slice v has for \tilde{v} 's allocation at the NE as

$$E^{ne}(v, \tilde{v}) \doteq U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ne,v})$$

Then, the following is satisfied: $E^{ne}(v, \tilde{v}) \leq 0.060$. Furthermore, there is a game instance where $E^{ne}(v, \tilde{v}) \geq 0.041$.

IV. GREET SLICE STRATEGY

In addition to the equilibrium and convergence issues highlighted in Theorems 2 and 1, a drawback of the Best Response algorithm analyzed in Section III is its complexity. Indeed, to determine its best response, a slice needs to solve a convex optimization problem. This strays from the simple algorithms, both in terms of implementation and understanding, that get adopted in practice and tenants tend to prefer. In this section, we propose an alternative slice strategy to the best response, which we refer to as the *GREET weight allocation policy*. This policy complements the resource allocation mechanism proposed in Section II, leading to the overall GREET framework

⁴Note that an implication of Theorem 1 is that the network slicing game is not ordinal potential game. This can be proved by contradiction: if this was an ordinal potential game, it would necessarily converge; as the theorem shows that the best response dynamics for the game do not converge, then this not an ordinal game and a potential function does not exist.

Algorithm 1 GREET weight allocation round for slice v

```
1: for user  $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$  do set  $\underline{f}_u \leftarrow \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u}$ 
2: for each base station  $b \in \mathcal{B}$  do set  $\underline{f}_b^v \leftarrow \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} \underline{f}_u$ 
3: for user  $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$  do
4:   if  $l_b^{-v} + \underline{f}_b^v \leq 1$  then set  $\underline{w}_u \leftarrow \frac{\underline{f}_u}{1 - \underline{f}_b^v} l_b^{-v}$ 
5:   else
6:     if  $s_b^v \geq \underline{f}_b^v$  then set  $\underline{w}_u \leftarrow \underline{f}_u$ 
7:     else set  $\underline{w}_u \leftarrow$  expression given by (6)
8: if  $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \underline{w}_u \leq s^v$  then
9:   for user  $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$  do
10:    set  $w_u \leftarrow \underline{w}_u + \phi_u (s^v - \sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \underline{w}_{u'})$ 
11: else
12:   while  $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} w_u \leq s^v$  do
13:    select users in order of increasing  $\underline{w}_u$ 
14:    set  $w_u \leftarrow \underline{w}_u$ 
```

consisting of two pieces: the resource allocation mechanism and the weight allocation policy.

A. Algorithm definition and properties

The GREET resource allocation given in Section II depends on the aggregate weight that slices allocate at each base station. In the following, we propose the *GREET weight allocation policy* to determine how each slice allocates its weights across its users and base stations. We first determine the weights of all the users of the slice, and then compute the aggregate weights by summing the weights of all the users at each base station, i.e., $l_b^v = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} w_u$.

Under the proposed GREET weight allocation, slices decide the weight allocations of their users based on two parameters: one that determines the minimum allocation of a user (γ_u) and another one that determines how extra resources should be prioritized (ϕ_u). A slice first assigns each user u the weight needed to meet its minimum rate requirement γ_u . Then, the slice allocates its remaining share amongst its users in proportion to their priority ϕ_u . Note that this algorithm does not require revealing each slice's aggregate weights to the others but only the base stations' overall loads, which discloses very limited information about slices' individual weights and leads to low signaling overheads. The algorithm is formally defined as follows.

Definition 4. (GREET Weight Allocation) Suppose that each slice v has access to the following three aggregate values for each base station: l_b^{-v} , $\sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \Delta_b^{v'}$ and $\sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \min(s_b^{v'}, l_b^{v'})$. Then, the GREET weight allocation is given by the weight computation determined by Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 realizes the basic insight presented earlier. The slice, say v , first computes the minimum resource allocation required to satisfy the minimum rate requirement of each user, denoted by \underline{f}_u . These are then summed to obtain the minimum aggregate requirement at each base station, denoted by \underline{f}_b^v (see Lines 1-2 of the algorithm).

Next, it computes the minimum weight for each user to meet the above requirements, denoted by \underline{w}_u . If $l_b^{-v} + \underline{f}_b^v \leq 1$, the GREET resource allocation is given by (1), and slice v 's minimum aggregate weight at base station b , l_b^v , should satisfy

$\frac{l_b^v}{l_b^{-v} + l_b^{-v}} = \underline{f}_b^v$. Hence, the minimum weight for user u at base station b is given by $\underline{w}_u = \frac{\underline{f}_u}{\underline{f}_b^v} l_b^v = \frac{\underline{f}_u}{1 - \underline{f}_b^v} l_b^{-v}$ (Line 4).

If $l_b^{-v} + \underline{f}_b^v > 1$, the GREET resource allocation is given by (2) and two cases need to be considered. In the first case, where the minimum resource allocation satisfies $\underline{f}_b^v \leq s_b^v$, it suffices to set $l_b^v = \underline{f}_b^v$ and $\underline{w}_u = \underline{f}_u$ and GREET resource allocation will make sure the requirement is met (Line 6). In the second case, where $\underline{f}_b^v > s_b^v$, in order to meet the minimal rate requirements under the GREET allocation given by (2), the minimum aggregate weight l_b^v must satisfy

$$s_b^v + \frac{(l_b^v - s_b^v) \left(1 - s_b^v - \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \min(s_b^{v'}, l_b^{v'}) \right)}{l_b^v - s_b^v + \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \Delta_b^{v'}} = \underline{f}_b^v.$$

Solving the above for l_b^v and allocating user weights in proportion to \underline{f}_u gives the following minimum weights (Line 7):

$$\underline{w}_u = \frac{\underline{f}_u}{\underline{f}_b^v} \left(s_b^v + \frac{(\underline{f}_b^v - s_b^v) \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \Delta_b^{v'}}{1 - \underline{f}_b^v - \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b \setminus \{v\}} \min(s_b^{v'}, l_b^{v'})} \right). \quad (6)$$

Once we have computed the minimum weight requirement for all users, we proceed as follows. If the slice's overall share s^v suffices to meet the requirements of all users, we divide the remaining share among the slice's users proportionally to their ϕ_u (Line 10). Otherwise, we assign weights such that we maximize the number of users that see their minimum rate requirement met, selecting users in order of increasing \underline{w}_u and providing them with the minimum weight \underline{w}_u (Lines 13-14).

Theorem 4 lends support to the GREET weight allocation algorithm. It shows that, under some relevant scenarios, this algorithm captures the character of social optimal slice allocations. Furthermore, in a network with many slices where the overall share of an individual slice is very small in relative terms, Theorem 5 shows that GREET is a good approximation to a slice's best response, suggesting that a slice cannot gain (substantially) by deviating from GREET. These results thus confirm that, in addition to being simple, GREET provides close to optimal performance both at a global level (across the whole network) as well as locally (for each individual slice).

Theorem 4. Suppose that all users are elastic and user utilities are logarithmic, i.e., $\alpha = 1$. Suppose GREET weight allocations converge to an equilibrium, which we denote by GREET equilibrium (GE). Then, GREET provides all users with the same rate allocation as that resulting from the socially optimal weights, i.e., $r_u(\mathbf{w}^{ge}) = r_u(\mathbf{w}^{so}), \forall u$, where \mathbf{w}^{so} is the (not necessarily unique) socially optimal weight allocation and \mathbf{w}^{ge} is the weight allocation under GREET equilibrium.

Theorem 5. Suppose that all the users of a slice are elastic, user utilities are logarithmic (i.e., $\alpha = 1$) and $s^v/l_b^{-v} < \delta \forall b$. Then, the following holds for all users u on slice v :

$$\frac{w_u^{br}(\mathbf{w}^{-v})}{1 + \delta} < w_u^g(\mathbf{w}^{-v}) < (1 + \delta) w_u^{br}(\mathbf{w}^{-v}),$$

where $\mathbf{w}^{br,v}(\mathbf{w}^{-v}) = (w_u^{br}(\mathbf{w}^{-v}) : u \in \mathcal{U}^v)$ is the best response of slice v to the other slices' weights \mathbf{w}^{-v} and similarly $\mathbf{w}^{g,v}(\mathbf{w}^{-v})$ is slice v 's response under GREET.

Further, suppose that GREET converges to an equilibrium. Then the resulting allocation is an ε -equilibrium with $\varepsilon = \log(1 + \delta)$.

The following results shows that, in contrast to the NE allocations analyzed in Section III, the GREET allocations are envy-free (see [12] for a formal definition of envy-freeness in the slicing context).

Theorem 6. Consider a setting where slices satisfy Assumption 2 and slices' GREET weight allocations converge to a GREET Equilibrium (GE). Suppose two slices v and \tilde{v} have the same guaranteed and excess shares, and that slice v has users with logarithmic utilities, i.e., $\alpha = 1$. Let $\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}$ denote the rate allocations to slice v 's users under at the GE and $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v$ their rate allocations after slices v and \tilde{v} exchange their overall allocations at the equilibrium. Then the envy that slice v has for \tilde{v} 's allocation at the GE satisfies

$$E^{ge}(v, \tilde{v}) \doteq U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}) \leq 0.$$

One of the main goals of the GREET resource allocation model proposed in Section II, in combination with the GREET weight allocation policy proposed in this section, is to provide guarantees to different slices, so that they can in turn ensure that the minimum rate requirements of their users are met. The lemma below confirms that, as long as slices are well dimensioned, GREET will achieve this goal.

Lemma 3. When Assumption 1 holds, the resource allocation resulting from combining the GREET resource allocation model with the GREET weight allocation policy meets all users' minimum rate requirements.

B. Convergence of the algorithm

A key desirable property for a slice-based weight allocation policy is convergence to an equilibrium. Applying a similar argument to that of Theorem 1, it can be shown that the GREET weight allocation algorithm need not converge. However, below we will show sufficient conditions for convergence.

Let $\mathbf{w}(n)$ be the overall weight allocation for update round n . Our goal is to show that the weight sequence $\mathbf{w}(n)$ converges when $n \rightarrow \infty$. The following theorem provides a sufficient condition for geometric convergence to a unique equilibrium. According to the theorem, convergence is guaranteed as long as (i) slice shares are well dimensioned, and (ii) the guaranteed fraction of resources for a given slice at any base station is limited. The second condition essentially says that there should be quite a bit of flexibility when managing guaranteed resources, leaving sufficient resources not committed to any slice. In practice, this may be appropriate in networks supporting slices with elastic traffic (which need non-committed resources), inelastic traffic (which may require some safety margins), or combinations thereof.

Theorem 7. Suppose that Assumption 1 holds and the maximum aggregate resource requirement per slice, f_{\max} , satisfies

$$f_{\max} := \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \max_{b \in \mathcal{B}} f_b^v < \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{V}| - 1}. \quad (7)$$

Then, if slices perform GREET-based updates of their weight allocations according to Algorithm 1, either in Round Robin manner or simultaneously, the sequence of weight vectors $(\mathbf{w}(n) : n \in \mathbb{N})$ converges to a unique fixed point, denoted by \mathbf{w}^* , irrespective of the initial weight allocation $\mathbf{w}(0)$. Furthermore, the convergence is geometric, i.e.,

$$\max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(n) - l_b^{v,*}| \leq \xi^n \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(0) - l_b^{v,*}| \quad (8)$$

where $\xi := \frac{2(|\mathcal{V}|-1)f_{\max}}{1-f_{\max}}$ and $l_b^{v,*}$ corresponds to slice v 's aggregate weights at the fixed point \mathbf{w}^* . Note that (7) imposes $\xi < 1$.

This convergence result can be further generalized under the asynchronous update model in continuous time [40]. Specifically, without loss of generality, let n index the sequence of times $(t_n, n \in \mathbb{N})$ at which one or more slices update their weight allocations and let \mathcal{N}^v denote the subset of those indices where slice v performs an update. For $n \in \mathcal{N}^v$, slice v updates its weights allocations based on possibly outdated weights for other slices, denoted by $(\mathbf{w}^{v'}(\tau_{v'}^v(n)) : v' \neq v)$, where $0 \leq \tau_{v'}^v(n) \leq n$ indexes the update associated with the most recent slice v' weight updates available to slice v prior to the n^{th} update. As long as the updates are performed according to the assumption below, one can show that GREET converges under such asynchronous updates.

Assumption 3. (Asynchronous updates) We assume that asynchronous updates are performed such that, for each slice $v \in \mathcal{V}$, the update sequence satisfies (i) $|\mathcal{N}^v| = \infty$, and (ii) for any subsequence $\{n_k\} \subset \mathcal{N}^v$ that tends to infinity, then $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tau_{v'}^v(n_k) = \infty, \forall v' \in \mathcal{V}$.

Theorem 8. Under Assumption 1, if slices perform GREET-based updates of their weight allocations asynchronously but satisfying Assumption 3, and if (7) holds, then the sequence of weight updates $(\mathbf{w}(n) : n \in \mathbb{N})$ converges to a unique fixed point irrespective of the initial condition.

While the above results provide some sufficient conditions for convergence, in the simulations performed we observed that, beyond these sufficient conditions, the algorithm always converges quite quickly under normal circumstances (within a few rounds). To show this, we run GREET over two artificial network settings with different user distributions and minimal rate requirements leading to different ξ . The results are illustrated in Fig. 1, where the 'theoretical upperbound' is the distance computed as the R.H.S. of (8). We observe that the actual convergence of GREET is geometric, but with a rate significantly greater than the theoretical bound. Furthermore, even with a $\xi > 1$, GREET still converges in a geometric manner, even though the theoretical results do not guarantee convergence in this case. Based on this, we adopt an approach for the GREET weight allocation algorithm where we let the weights be updated by each slice for a number of rounds, and stop the algorithm if it has not converged upon reaching this number (which is set to 7 in our simulations).

C. Practical Implementation Considerations

The GREET approach proposed in this paper can be implemented in real networks using a similar technology as

Fig. 1: Actual L^1 norm of the distance to the fixed point under GREET vs. the theoretical upper bound provided by Theorem 7.

that used for SONET (Self-Organizing Networks) [15]. In particular, SONET collects information in real time about the entire network, including user association and base station load, and uses such information to periodically optimize the network configuration, including resource allocation to end-users in each base station. Our approach has similar requirements, conveying base station load information to a centralized location where the GREET algorithm can run and compute the desired resource allocation, which can then be realized in the various base stations. The frequency of updates in SONET may be in the order of minutes, which is also a good choice for our setting.

Changes in the loads across base stations will typically occur due to two mechanisms. On one hand we may have user arrivals, departures and handoffs leading to fairly dramatic changes in load particularly when each base stations supports a relatively small set of users. On the other hand changes in the users' channels, e.g., fading/shadowing, will impact the effective load they impose on the system. In general the time scales of the former would be much slower than those on which the system will adapt to channel variations. We envisage our framework implements its updates to track variations in the number of users and changes in *averages* of users' channel quality, i.e., relatively slowly. However in Section V-E we evaluate via simulation the impact that varying the update rate has on the network's resulting performance.

It is worth pointing out that many iterations of the algorithm can be done very quickly since they need not be implemented until the algorithm converges. For example, we can bring all the information of the network to a centralized server where we run the iterative interactive process in which the infrastructure provider interacts with tenants along several rounds to determine the resource allocation across the entire network. Once this process ends, the resulting allocation can be pushed to base stations to implement it. This is not unlike a typical software defined network or self-organized-network setting.

Another relevant point from a practical perspective is the information that is shared with slices. The proposed mechanism requires relatively limited information per base station for each tenant, which corresponds to the overall load of other slices and the overall excess weight (i.e., load above the guaranteed shares across base stations) and the aggregate

min of the slice shares and current loads. Importantly, this information does not have any per-slice information. Overall this is a relatively limited amount of information scaling with the number of base stations rather than the number of users on the network, allowing tenants to preserve private information.

Even though we are not forcing tenants to use the GREET resource allocation, and they are free to apply any strategy they choose, we envisage that tenants are likely to employ GREET resource allocation due to its desirable properties. First of all, GREET resource allocation is simple, which is typically an important requirement for tenants. Furthermore, it provides tenants with substantial flexibility and is very close to the best response (for some settings). When all slices employ GREET resource allocation, desirable properties are achieved in terms of overall network performance, such as social optimal performance and convergence (for some settings).

Finally, we would like to point out that the intent of GREET is not to determine how to make detailed scheduling decisions to users, but instead to determine the overall fraction of each base stations's resources to be allocated to each slice. Once the overall fractions are determined, they can be used in different ways. For example these overall weights per slice can be the slice weights of a traditional GPS scheduler. Alternatively, one could consider giving tenants the ability to customize the way traffic in their slices is scheduled at base stations accounting e.g. for delay requirements. This type of customization is an essential part of network slicing which may need to support very diverse types of traffic and requirements, yet is a complementary part of our paper which addresses allocation of resources across slices.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section we present a detailed performance evaluation of GREET.

A. Mobile Network Simulation Setup

Simulation model: We simulate a dense 'small cell' wireless deployment following the IMT-Advanced evaluation guidelines [41]. The network consists of 19 base stations in a hexagonal cell layout with an inter-site distance of 20 meters and 3 sector antennas; thus, \mathcal{B} corresponds to 57 sectors. Users associate to the sector offering the strongest SINR, where the downlink SINR between base station b and user u is modeled as in [42]: $\text{SINR}_{bu} = \frac{P_b G_{bu}}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{B} \setminus \{b\}} P_k G_{ku} + \sigma^2}$, where, following [41], the noise σ^2 is set to -104dB , the transmit power P_b is equal to 41dB and the channel gain between sector b and user u , denoted by G_{bu} , accounts for path loss, shadowing, fast fading and antenna gain. The path loss is given by $36.7 \log_{10}(d_{bu}) + 22.7 + 26 \log_{10}(f_c)\text{dB}$, where d_{bu} denotes the current distance in meters from the user u to sector b , and the carrier frequency f_c is equal to 2.5GHz . The antenna gain is set to 17dBi , shadowing is updated every second and modeled by a log-normal distribution with standard deviation of 8dB [42]; and fast fading follows a Rayleigh distribution depending on the mobile's speed and the angle of incidence. The achievable rate c_u for user u at a given point in time is based on a discrete set of modulation and coding schemes (MCS), with the associated SINR thresholds

Fig. 2: Comparison of GREET against the benchmark approaches in terms of the overall Utility U and the outage probability $P(\text{outage})$.

given in [43]. This MCS value is selected based on the average SINR_{bu} , where channel fast fading is averaged over a second. For user scheduling, we assume that resource blocks are assigned to users in a round-robin manner proportionally to the allocation determined by the resource allocation policy under consideration.⁵ For user mobility, we consider two different mobility patterns: Random Waypoint model (RWP) [44], yielding roughly uniform load distributions, and SLAW model [45], typically yielding clustered users and thus non-uniform load distributions.

Performance metrics: Recall that our primary goal is to give slices flexibility in meeting their users' minimum rate requirements while optimizing the overall network efficiency. To assess the effectiveness of GREET in achieving this goal, we focus on the following two metrics:

- **Outage probability $P(\text{outage})$:** this is the probability that a user does not meet its minimum rate requirement. In order for a slice to provide a reliable service, this probability should be kept below a certain threshold.
- **Overall utility U :** this is given by (4) and reflects the overall performance across all slices.

State-of-the-art approaches: In order to show the advantages of GREET, we will compare it to the following benchmarks:

- **Reservation-based approach:** with this approach, each slice v reserves a local share at each base station b , denoted by \hat{s}_b^v . The resources at each base station are then shared among the *active* slices (having at least one user) in proportion to the local shares \hat{s}_b^v . This is akin to setting weights for a Generalized Processor Sharing in a resource [46] and is in line with the spirit of reservation-based schemes in the literature [1]–[8].
- **Share-based approach:** with this approach, each slice gets a share \tilde{s}^v of the overall resources, as in [10]–[14]. Specifically, resources at each base station are shared according to the scheme proposed in [10], where each slice $v \in \mathcal{V}$ distributes its share \tilde{s}^v equally amongst all its active users $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$, such that each user u gets a weight $\tilde{w}_u = \tilde{s}^v / |\mathcal{U}^v|$, and then, at each base station

⁵Our performance evaluation focuses on a setting where active users are infinitely backlogged. However, if a user becomes inactive or is not backlogged, the scheduling algorithm can easily track this and redistribute the rate of such a user across other users in the same slice.

$b \in \mathcal{B}$ the resources are allocated in proportion to users' weights.

- **Social optimal:** this scheme corresponds to the social optimal weight allocation \mathbf{w}^{so} given by (5) under GREET resource allocation.
- **Best-response dynamics:** in this approach, each slice updates its Best Response sequentially while the network performs GREET resource allocation. Note that even if Lemma 1 shows that such updates are not guaranteed to converge, we checked that in all our simulations we converge to a Nash Equilibrium. Note that, since the conditions of [39] are satisfied under certain conditions, in such cases the algorithm of [39] could be employed as an alternative to the Best-response dynamics to reach a Nash Equilibrium.

In order to meet the desired performance targets, the shares employed in the above approaches are dimensioned as follows. We consider two types of slices: (i) those which provide their users with minimum rate requirements, which we refer to as *guaranteed service slices*, and (ii) those which do not provide minimum rate requirements, which we refer to as *elastic service slices*. In GREET, for guaranteed service slices, we define a maximum acceptable outage probability P_{max} and determine the necessary share at each base station, s_b^v , such that $P(\text{outage}) \leq P_{max}$, assuming that the number of users follow a Poisson distribution whose mean is obtained from the simulated user traces; for these slices, we set $e^v = 0$. For elastic service slices, we set $s_b^v = 0 \forall b$ and e^v to a value that determines the mean rate provided to elastic users. For the reservation-based approach, we set $\hat{s}_b^v = s_b^v$ for guaranteed service slices, to provide the same guarantees as GREET; for elastic service slices, we set \hat{s}_b^v such that (i) their sum is equal to e^v , to provide the same total share as GREET, (ii) the sum of the \hat{s}_b^v 's at each base station does not exceed 1, to preserve the desired service guarantees, and (iii) they are as much balanced as possible across all base stations, within these two constraints. Finally, for the share-based approach we set $\tilde{s}^v = s^v$ for all slice types, i.e., the same shares as GREET.

B. Comparison with state-of-the-art benchmarks

Fig. 2 exhibits the performance of GREET versus the above benchmarks in terms of $P(\text{outage})$ and overall utility U for the following scenario: (i) we have two guaranteed service and two elastic service slices; (ii) the share of elastic service slices is increased within the range $s^v \in [2, 19]$; (iii) the minimum rate requirement for users on the guaranteed service slices is set to $\gamma_u = 0.2 \text{ Mbps } \forall u$; (iv) the shares of guaranteed service slices are dimensioned to satisfy an outage probability threshold P_{max} of 0.01; (v) for all slices, the priorities ϕ_u of all users are equal; and, (vi) the users of the elastic service slices follow the RWP model, leading to roughly uniform spatial loads, while the users of the guaranteed service slices have non-uniform loads as given by the SLAW model. Since user utilities are not defined below the minimum rate requirements, the computation of the overall utility only takes into account the users whose minimum rate requirements are satisfied under all schemes.

The results show that GREET outperforms both the share- and reservation-based approaches. While the share-based ap-

proach can flexibly shift resources across base stations, leading to a good overall utility, it is not able to sufficiently isolate slices from one another, resulting in large outage probabilities, $P(\text{outage})$, as the share of elastic service slices increase. By contrast, the reservation-based approach is effective in keeping $P(\text{outage})$ under control (albeit a bit above the threshold due to the approximation in the computation of s_b^v). However, since it relies on local decisions, it cannot globally optimize allocations and is penalized in terms of the overall utility. GREET achieves the best of both worlds: it meets the service requirements, keeping $P(\text{outage})$ well below the P_{max} threshold, while achieving a utility that matches that of the share-based approach. Moreover, it performs very close to the social optimal, albeit with somewhat larger $P(\text{outage})$ due to the fact that the social optimal imposes the minimum rate requirements as constraints, forcing each slice to help the others meeting their minimum rate requirements, while in GREET each slice behaves ‘selfishly’.

As can be seen in the subplot of Fig. 2 the GREET allocation outperforms that of the Best-Response dynamics in overall utility achieved and is very close in the outage probability. Specifically, GREET achieves relative gain in social utility from 16% to 36%, at the cost of a $P(\text{outage})$ less than 0.005. This observation is robust to a range of different network loads.

C. Outage probability gains

One of the main observations of the experiment conducted above is that GREET provides substantial gains in terms of outage probability over the shared-based scheme. In order to obtain additional insights on these gains, we analyze them for a variety of scenarios comprising the following settings:

- *Uniform*: we have two guaranteed service slices and two elastic service slices; the users’ mobility on all slices follow the RWP model and have the same priority ϕ_u .
- *Heterogeneous Aligned*: the users of all slices are distributed non-uniformly according to SLAW but they all follow the same distribution (i.e., slices have the same hotspots).
- *Heterogeneous Orthogonal*: all slices are distributed according to SLAW model but each slice follows a different distribution (i.e., slices have different hotspots).
- *Mixed*: we have the same scenario as in Fig. 2, with the only difference that for one of the guaranteed service slices we have that all users are inelastic, i.e., the priority ϕ_u of all of them is set to 0.

For the above network configurations, we vary the share s^v of elastic service slices while keeping the shares for the guaranteed service slices fixed.

We evaluated the absolute performance in terms of the outage probability. The evaluation results show that GREET achieves less than 1% outage probability in all four scenarios we simulated and has a $P(\text{outage})$ of approximately 0.2% for most cases.

Fig. 3 shows the ratio of the $P(\text{outage})$ of the share-based approach over that of GREET as a function of the overall share of elastic slices, i.e., $\sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}_e} s^v$, where \mathcal{V}_e is the set of elastic service slices. Results are given with 95% confidence intervals but they are so small that can barely be seen. We observe that GREET outperforms the share-based approach in

Fig. 3: Gain in $P(\text{outage})$ over the share-based approach, measured as the ratio of $P(\text{outage})$ under the share-based approach over that under GREET.

Fig. 4: Gain in $P(\text{outage})$ over the reservation-based approach, measured as the ratio of $P(\text{outage})$ under the reservation-based approach over that under GREET.

all cases, providing $P(\text{outage})$ values up to one order of magnitude smaller. As expected, the gain in $P(\text{outage})$ grows as the the share of elastic service slices increases; indeed, as the share-based approach does not provide resource guarantees, it cannot control the outage probability of guaranteed service slices. Also, the least gain in outage probability was obtained under *Uniform* scenario, and is significantly better under other scenarios, which is consistent with the observation of absolute $P(\text{outage})$ achieved by GREET. This is mainly because under *Uniform* scenario the user distribution might not be severely imbalanced across the network, and the service guarantee is mostly obtained via share dimensioning.

Fig. 4 further compares the performance of GREET against the reservation-based approach in terms of $P(\text{outage})$, by showing the ratio of the $P(\text{outage})$ of the reservation-based approach over that of GREET. As expected, GREET offers a comparable performance to that of the reservation-based approach, since both approaches have been dimensioned to achieve a very small $P(\text{outage})$. In particular, when overall elastic slice share is between 5 to 15, the reservation-based approach beats GREET by a factor approximately 2, which translates to a margin in $P(\text{outage})$ of the order of 0.0001 in our simulation. Meanwhile, when the elastic slice share ramps up to over 20, GREET starts to offer lower $P(\text{outage})$ than the reservation-based approach in all 4 network configurations. This is because the mismatch between RWP/SLAW model

and Poisson distribution assumed in dimensioning the share allocation of the reservation-based approach becomes more significant. Note that while the differences in relative terms are not necessarily negligible, since in all cases the $P(\text{outage})$ values are very low, the differences in absolute terms are indeed very small.

D. Utility gains

In order to gain additional insight on the utility gains over the reservation-based and the share-based schemes, we evaluated the absolute performance in terms of overall utility. GREET resource allocation achieves best overall utility of around 0.6 under the *Heterogeneous Orthogonal* scenario, where GREET can best exploit the underutilized resources opportunistically. Under *Uniform* scenario, the overall utility achieved was between -0.1 and -0.2 with overall share of elastic slices ranging from 5 to 30.

In Fig. 5a we analyze the utility gains over the reservation-based approach for the scenarios introduced above. The gain in utility was measured as the utility under GREET minus that under the benchmark approach. Results show that GREET consistently outperforms the reservation-based scheme across all approaches and share configurations, achieving similar gains in terms of overall utility in all cases. This confirms that, by providing the ability to dynamically adjust the overall resource allocation to the current user distribution across base stations, GREET can achieve significant utility gains over the reservation-based approach. The utility gains can be interpreted as savings of capacity required to achieve the same utility, under different resource allocation scheme.

Definition 5. *In a network slicing setup, the capacity saving factor of one resource sharing scheme (denoted by the user fraction vector) \mathbf{f}_1 over another \mathbf{f}_2 is the minimal amount of scaling we need to apply to \mathbf{c} to make the social utility under the first scheme $U(\mathbf{f}_2; \mathbf{c})$ equal to that under the second scheme $U(\mathbf{f}_1; \mathbf{c})$. Formally,*

$$\epsilon_{1,2} = \min\{\epsilon > 0 \mid U(\mathbf{f}_1; \mathbf{c}) \leq U(\mathbf{f}_2; \epsilon \mathbf{c})\} \quad (9)$$

is defined as the capacity saving factor of \mathbf{f}_1 over \mathbf{f}_2 under \mathbf{c} .

In Fig. 5a, the capacity saving factor ranges from 1.08 to 1.62, meaning that GREET uses 8% ~ 62% less capacity to achieve the same utility than reservation-based approaches.

We also evaluated the empirical user rate distribution of a typical user for our simulation setup, see Fig. 5c. As shown in the figure, users under GREET and the shared based approach (overlapping curves) can better leverage surplus resources in under-utilized base stations, leading to a moderate improvement in the fraction of users who perceive higher rates versus what is achieved by the reservation based approach. Thus the gains in reduced outage, do not come at a penalty in the user perceived rates.

Fig. 5b further compares the utility under GREET and that under the share-based approach. We observe that the difference in utilities are very small, which means that the share-based approach offers a very similar performance to GREET in terms of utility. A closer look reveals that, although the share-based approach can adapt to dynamic user distribution very well, GREET still consistently achieves better

utility under all network configurations except for the *Mixed* scenario.

E. Impact of resource allocation update rate

One of the practical considerations when implementing GREET weight allocation is whether resource allocation updates carried out in the system control plane can keep up with user mobility, e.g., changes in users associations to base stations, and associated changes in wireless channel, e.g., changes in the path loss. While the update frequency for slice-level resource allocation that is achievable will depend on the physical layer, network and details of the actual implementation of the system, and thus is out of the scope of this paper, we can still evaluate the efficiency of GREET for different update rates via its impact on the utility and outage probability.

In our evaluation, we used the *Uniform* network scenario, and let the system update user weights only once in every x seconds, where x ranges from one second (which means there's no delay at all), to 120 seconds. We call x the update period. Each user carries its weight after being allocated, and at each base station, the resource is shared according to the algorithm in Def. 2. In order to understand the impact of the update period on utility, we set all 4 slices to be elastic slices.

The results are exhibited in Fig. 6. As can be seen the performance of GREET was indeed negatively impacted if the resource allocation scheme update rate is limited. There is a drop in utility when increasing the update period but this drop is not very large and more importantly, it stabilizes for update periods greater 30 seconds. When the update period is above 2 minutes, the overall utility is no longer monotonic with the update period. This is because there are other aspects, aside from the update period length, that impact the overall utility.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

GREET provides a flexible framework for managing heterogeneous performance requirements for network slices supporting dynamic user populations on a shared infrastructure. It is a practical approach that provides slices with sufficient resource guarantees to meet their requirements, and at the same time it allows them to unilaterally and dynamically customize their allocations to their current users' needs, thus achieving a good tradeoff between isolation and overall network efficiency. We view the GREET approach proposed here as a component of the overall solution to network slicing. Such a solution should include interfaces linking the resource allocation policies proposed here to lower level resource schedulers, which may possibly be opportunistic and delay-sensitive. Of particular interest will be the interfaces geared at supporting ultra-high reliability and with ultra-low latency services.

APPENDIX: PROOFS OF THE THEOREMS

Proof of Lemma 1

We first show that there exists a weight setting that meets the minimum rate requirements of all users. As long as a fraction of base station b equal to s_b^v is sufficient to meet the user minimum rate requirements, by applying an aggregate weight equal to s_b^v in the resource, the tenant is guaranteed

(a) Gain in utility over the reservation-based approach, measured as the utility under GREET minus that under the reservation-based approach.

(b) Gain in utility over the share-based approach, measured as the utility under GREET minus that under the share-based approach.

(c) Empirical CDF of typical user rate allocation when elastic share is 4.9 under *Uniform* scenario

Fig. 5: Numerical results on utilities and user rate allocation.

Fig. 6: Overall utility under GREET resource allocations when the update period (in seconds) for user weights is limited.

to get this fraction of resources. As this can be applied to all resources, the minimum rate guarantees can be met for all the users of the tenant.

The optimization problem is given by the maximization of the sum of user utilities. This is a concave function on the weights as long as the individual user utilities are concave. As long as the minimum rate requirements are satisfied, individual user utilities are concave, as they are increasing concave function of a concave function (see [47]). The set of feasible weights need to satisfy $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} w_u \leq s^v$ and $w_u \geq 0, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$, and need to be such that the minimum rate requirements are satisfied. The latter imposes $w_u / \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b} w_u \geq \gamma_u$ which yields $w_u - \gamma_u \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b} w_u \geq 0, \forall u$. As a result, the set of feasible weights is convex.

Proof of Lemma 2

We next prove that $w_u \geq \delta$ does not hold, we may not have a NE. Consider a scenario with two slices, 1 and 2, and two base stations, a and b. Each slice has a user in each base station such that $\gamma_{1a} = \gamma_{2a} = 1/4$ and $\gamma_{1b} = \gamma_{2b} = 0$. Furthermore, we have $\phi_{1a} = \phi_{2a} = 0, \phi_{1b} = \phi_{2b} = 1, s_a^1 = s_a^2 = 1, s_b^1 = s_b^2 = 0$ and $e^1 = e^2 = 0$. In the best response, it holds $w_{1a} = w_{1b}/3$ and $w_{1b} = w_{1a}/3$, which implies that there exists no NE.

Proof of Theorem 1

Let us consider a scenario with three slices, denoted by Slices 1, 2 and 3, and three base stations, denoted by Base

Station (BS) a, b, and c, respectively. Slice 1 has two users, one at BS a, another at BS b, denoted by 1a and 1b, respectively. Slice 2 has two users, one at BS b, another at BS c, denoted by 2b and 2c. Also, Slice 3 has two users at BS a and c, respectively, denoted by 3a and 3c. The share allocation is $s^1 = s^2 = s^3 = 3/4 + \epsilon$ for some $\delta < \epsilon < 1/4, s_a^1 = s_b^2 = s_c^3 = 3/4, \gamma_{1a} = \gamma_{2b} = \gamma_{3c} = 3/4, \gamma_{1b} = \gamma_{2c} = \gamma_{3a} = 0, \phi_{1a} = \phi_{2b} = \phi_{3c} = 0$ and $\phi_{1b} = \phi_{2c} = \phi_{3a} = 1$.

It can be seen that a NE in the above scenario is given by $w_{1a} = w_{2b} = w_{3c} = 9/16 + 3\epsilon/4$ and $w_{1b} = w_{2c} = w_{3a} = 3/16 + \epsilon/4$.

Let us start with $w_{3a} > 1/4$ and apply the best response starting with slice 1 followed by 2 and 3. Slice 1 takes $w_{1a} = 3/4$ and $w_{1b} = \epsilon$. In turn, slice 2 selects $w_{2b} = 3\epsilon$ and $w_{2c} = 3/4 - 2\epsilon > 1/4$. This yields $w_{3c} = 3/4$ and $w_{3a} = \epsilon$. We thus enter an endless cycle where w_{1a}, w_{2b} and w_{3c} alternate the values of $3/4$ with 3ϵ .

Proof of Theorem 2

This theorem follows from Theorem 4 in [12]. In particular when the network has only elastic users with logarithmic utilities, the GREET slice-based resource allocation proposed in this paper coincides with the resource allocation mechanism proposed in [12]. Thus by Theorem 4 of [12] we have that

$$U(\mathbf{w}^{so}) - U(\mathbf{w}^{ne}) \leq \log(e) \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} s^v. \quad (10)$$

Note that in [12] the weights are normalized so $\sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} s^v = 1$ but such a normalization is not required under GREET and hence we have the above result instead of $U(\mathbf{w}^{so}) - U(\mathbf{w}^{ne}) \leq \log(e)$ as in [12].

Proof of Theorem 3

This theorem is similar to Theorem 5 in [12], except that we need to address a setting with elastic, inelastic and rate adaptive users with guaranteed shares and a GREET-based resource allocation. Under Assumption 2 and considering the excess rate allocation to each user, i.e., those beyond the required guarantees, we will show that our problem reduces to that in Theorem 5.

Let \mathbf{w}^{ne} denote weight allocation at the NE and l_b^{ne} and $l_b^{ne,v}$ the overall load and the aggregate weight of slice v at base station b . Consider a user u of slice v in base station

b. The rate r_u^{ne} of user u at the NE under a GREET-based resource allocation satisfies one of the two following cases.

First, if the load at base station b satisfies $l_b^{ne} \leq 1$ the rate of a user u at this base station is given by

$$r_u^{ne} = \frac{w_u^{ne}}{l_b^{ne}} c_u.$$

Note from (3) that slice utility depends on $r_u^{ne} - \gamma_u$. We define the excess rate and the excess weight allocation to user u as $q_u^{ne} \doteq r_u^{ne} - \gamma_u$ and $m_u^{ne} \doteq w_u^{ne} - l_b^{ne} \gamma_u / c_u$, respectively, where $l_b^{ne} \gamma_u / c_u$ is the weight that user u needs in order to meet its minimal rate requirement γ_u when the load at b is l_b^{ne} . With this notation, we have that

$$q_u^{ne} = \frac{m_u^{ne}}{l_b^{ne}} c_u.$$

Second, if the load at base station b satisfies $l_b^{ne} > 1$, then the guaranteed share s_b^v is exactly what is needed to meet its users rate requirements at b (given that v is perfectly dimensioned). Thus, the excess rate of user u corresponds to the second term in (2), i.e.,

$$q_u^{ne} = \frac{m_u^{ne}}{\sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \Delta_b^{ne, v'}} \left(1 - \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \min[s_b^{v'}, l_b^{ne, v'}] \right) c_u$$

where the excess weight of user u is now given by $m_u^{ne} = w_u - \gamma_u / c_u$. If we define $\hat{c}_u \doteq c_u (1 - \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \min[s_b^{v'}, l_b^{ne, v'}])$ and $\hat{l}_b^{ne} \doteq \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}_b} \Delta_b^{ne, v'}$, the above can be rewritten as

$$q_u^{ne} = \frac{m_u^{ne}}{\hat{l}_b^{ne}} \hat{c}_u$$

Putting together the above two cases, the excess weights for users u on slice v are given by $m_u^{ne} = w_u - \min[l_b^{ne} \gamma_u / c_u, \gamma_u / c_u]$ and satisfy:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} m_u^{ne} = s^v - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \min \left[\frac{l_b^{ne} \gamma_u}{c_u}, \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u} \right].$$

Now recall that in this theorem we consider two slices v and \tilde{v} which have the same guaranteed and overall network shares and which exchange the resource allocations they achieved under the NE. We shall denote the rate and weight that a user u on slice v would receive under such an exchange by \tilde{r}_u and \tilde{w}_u , respectively. We shall only consider the cases where $\tilde{w}_u \geq \min[l_b^{ne} \gamma_u / c_u, \gamma_u / c_u]$, as otherwise slice v would not meet its users' rate requirements after the exchange with \tilde{v} .

Note that the weight allocations after the exchange, \tilde{w} , see base stations loads l^{ne} , so we can express the rates that the users of slice v after the exchange with \tilde{v} as follows. First, if $l_b^{ne} \leq 1$, we have

$$\tilde{q}_u = \frac{\tilde{m}_u}{l_b^{ne}} c_u$$

where \tilde{q}_u and \tilde{m}_u are the excess rate and weight of user u after v and \tilde{v} exchange resource allocations. Second, when $l_b^{ne} > 1$, we have that

$$\tilde{q}_u = \frac{\tilde{m}_u}{\hat{l}_b^{ne}} \hat{c}_u,$$

where the \tilde{m}_u for users on slice v must satisfy

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \tilde{m}_u = s^v - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \min \left[\frac{l_b^{ne} \gamma_u}{c_u}, \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u} \right]. \quad (11)$$

Note that expressions for the excess rates and constraints on the excess weights \mathbf{m}^{ne} and $\tilde{\mathbf{m}}$ are the same as if all the users of slice v were elastic. Indeed, at a base station where when $l_b^{ne} \leq 1$, the resource allocation criterion akin to one where all users were elastic users. Similarly, when $l_b^{ne} > 1$, we obtain the same expressions by taking \hat{c}_u and \hat{l}_b^{ne} instead of c_u and l_b^{ne} . The constraints on $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} m_u^{ne}$ and $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \tilde{m}_u$ are also equivalent to the case with elastic users, substituting the overall share s^v by the following expression: $s^v - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \min[l_b \gamma_u / c_u, \gamma_u / c_u]$.

Thus, by considering excess rates and weights, this makes the problem equivalent to the one where all users are elastic. Further, since slice v users are assumed to have logarithmic utilities, the envy associated with slice v and \tilde{v} resource exchange at the NE can be established via the result in Theorem 5 of [12], which proves this theorem.

Proof of Theorem 4

The utility of the network depends on the users' rates r_u . Since there is a direct mapping between the fraction of resources assigned to each user and its rate, we can express utility as a function of the fractions $f_u \forall u$, i.e., $U(\mathbf{f})$. When there is only elastic traffic in the network, the total utility is given by

$$U(\mathbf{f}) = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} s^{v(u)} \phi_u \log(f_u c_u) \quad \text{subject to} \quad \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b} f_u = 1 \quad \forall b,$$

where $v(u)$ is the slice user u belongs to.

The problem of maximizing the total utility subject to the above constraint is solved by Lemma 5.1 of [48], leading to

$$f_u = \frac{s^{v(u)} \phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}_{b(u)}} s^{v(u')} \phi_{u'}} \quad (12)$$

where $b(u)$ is the base station user u is associated with.

The above optimization did not impose the constraint on the weights of a slice, $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} w_u \leq s^v$, and hence in principle represents an upper bound on the total utility of the socially optimal allocation. However, the weights resulting from the optimization satisfy this constraint, which means that the allocation of (12) is the socially optimal allocation.

Note that the allocation of (12) coincides with the allocation resulting from GREET. Indeed, when all users are elastic GREET simply sets the share fractions proportionally to the ϕ_u values, while forcing that all share fractions add up to the slice's share s^v .

Proof of Theorem 5

Let us consider the best response and the GREET response of slice v when other slices and associated users choose a weight allocation \mathbf{w}^{-v} leading to per-base station overall load vector $\mathbf{1}^{-v}$. The best response to $\mathbf{1}^{-v}$ is the weight allocation that maximizes slice V 's utility, and the GREET response is the result of applying the GREET weight allocation algorithm.

When there is only elastic traffic in the network, the weight allocation to a user u on slice v under the best response to $\mathbf{1}^{-v}$ is given by [12],

$$w_u^{br}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) = s^v \frac{\phi_u \frac{l_{b(u)}^{-v}}{l_{b(u)}^{br, v} (\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u)}^{-v}}}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'} \frac{l_{b(u')}^{-v}}{l_{b(u')}^{br, v} (\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u')}^{-v}}}$$

where $b(u)$ denotes the base station serving user u .

Under elastic traffic, the GREET weight allocation algorithm simply sets the weights proportionally to the ϕ_u values, leading to the following GREET response:

$$w_u^g(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) = s^v \frac{\phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'}}$$

Noting that $l_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})/l_b^{-v} \leq s^v/l_b^{-v} < \delta$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} w_u^{br}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) &= s^v \frac{\phi_u \frac{l_{b(u)}^{-v}}{l_{b(u)}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u)}^{-v}}}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'} \frac{l_{b(u')}^{-v}}{l_{b(u')}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u')}^{-v}}} \\ &> s^v \frac{\phi_u \frac{l_{b(u)}^{-v}}{l_{b(u)}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u)}^{-v}}}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'}} > s^v \frac{\phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'}} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \delta} \right) \\ &= w_u^g(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) \left(\frac{1}{1 + \delta} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and similarly we have that

$$\begin{aligned} w_u^{br}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) &= s^v \frac{\phi_u \frac{l_{b(u)}^{-v}}{l_{b(u)}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u)}^{-v}}}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'} \frac{l_{b(u')}^{-v}}{l_{b(u')}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u')}^{-v}}} \\ &< s^v \frac{\phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'} \frac{l_{b(u')}^{-v}}{l_{b(u')}^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) + l_{b(u')}^{-v}}} \\ &\leq s^v \frac{\phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'}} (1 + \delta) = w_u^g(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) (1 + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

To show that the GREET equilibrium corresponds to an ε -equilibrium we proceed as follows. Let $f_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})$ be the fraction of resources obtained by slice v at base station b in the best response to $\mathbf{1}^{-v}$, and let $f_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})$ be the fraction of resources for the GREET response.

It follows that

$$f_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) = \frac{l_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})}{l_b^{-v} + l_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})}.$$

Given that the above is a monotonic increasing function in $l_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})$ and we have that $l_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) \leq l_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})(1 + \delta)$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} f_b^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}) &\leq \frac{l_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})(1 + \delta)}{l_b^{-v} + l_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})(1 + \delta)} \\ &< \frac{l_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})(1 + \delta)}{l_b^{-v} + l_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v})} = (1 + \delta) f_b^{g,v}(\mathbf{1}^{-v}). \end{aligned}$$

Both in the best response and the GREET response, the f_b^v resources at base station b are shared among the users of slice v at that base station proportionally to their ϕ_u 's. Note that the above holds for any setting of the other slices $\mathbf{1}^{-v}$.

In the argument below we will abuse notation to denote the utility of slice v as a function of the weights of v and those of the users of other slices as $U^v(\mathbf{w}^v, \mathbf{1}^{-v})$. Suppose that we have reached a GREET equilibrium (GE), with weights \mathbf{w}^{ge} , and that slice v deviates to take the best response to the base station loads under GE, $\mathbf{1}^{ge,-v}$. Then, we have the following:

$$U^v(\mathbf{w}^{br,v}, \mathbf{1}^{ge,-v}) = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_u \log(f_u^{br,v}(\mathbf{1}^{ge,-v}) c_u)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &< \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_u \log((1 + \delta) f_u^{ge,v}(\mathbf{1}^{ge,-v}) c_u) \\ &= U^v(\mathbf{w}^{ge,v}, \mathbf{1}^{ge,-v}) + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

where $\varepsilon \doteq \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_u \log(1 + \delta) = \log(1 + \delta)$.

Proof of Theorem 6

Let $\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}$ be the allocation to users of slice v under the GREET equilibrium and $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v$ be the utility maximizing rate allocation when slice v and \tilde{v} exchange the allocations at the GREET equilibrium. To show envy-freeness we need to show that $U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}) \geq U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v)$,

Following the development of Theorem 3, $U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge})$ can be expressed as follows:

$$U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge}) = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{m_u^{ge}}{l_b^{ge}} c_u\right) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{m_u^{ge}}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} \hat{c}_u\right)$$

where $m_u^{ge} = w_u^{ge} - \min[l_b^{ge} \gamma_u / c_u, \gamma_u / c_u]$ is the excess weight allocation to user u under GREET equilibrium, $\mathcal{U}^{v,1}$ is the set of users of slice v at base stations where $l_b^{ge} \leq 1$ and $\mathcal{U}^{v,2}$ is the set of users of slice v at base stations for where $l_b^{ge} > 1$. The quantities \hat{l}_b^{ge} , and \hat{c}_u are defined as in the proof of Theorem 3.

In order to characterize the user rate allocations that slice v would obtain with slice \tilde{v} 's resources, we shall find the split of the aggregate weight of \tilde{v} at each base station b to users $u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v$ of slice v that maximizes the utility of slice v . We let $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}^v$ denote this weight allocation, $\tilde{\mathbf{m}}^v$ the excess weights and $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v$ the resulting rates.

Following the development of Theorem 3 and using the assumption that slice v has logarithmic utilities, $U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}})$ can be expressed as follows:

$$U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}) = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{\tilde{m}_u}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} c_u\right) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{\tilde{m}_u}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} \hat{c}_u\right)$$

Let us consider the \tilde{m}_u values for $u \in \mathcal{U}^v$ that maximize $U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v})$ subject to the constraint given by (11). One can simplify $U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v})$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}) &= \\ &= \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{\tilde{m}_u}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} c_u\right) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{\tilde{m}_u}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} \hat{c}_u\right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{m_u^{ge}}{l_b^{ge}} c_u\right) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log\left(\frac{m_u^{ge}}{\hat{l}_b^{ge}} \hat{c}_u\right) \\ &= \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log(\tilde{m}_u c_u) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log(\tilde{m}_u \hat{c}_u) \\ &\quad - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log(m_u^{ge} c_u) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log(m_u^{ge} \hat{c}_u) \end{aligned}$$

Since the m_u^{ge} values are fixed, the above optimization is equivalent to finding the \tilde{m}_u values that maximize

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,1}} \phi_u \log(\tilde{m}_u c_u) + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^{v,2}} \phi_u \log(\tilde{m}_u \hat{c}_u)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \tilde{m}_u = s^v - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \min\left[\frac{l_b^{ge} \gamma_u}{c_u}, \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u}\right].$$

By solving the associated convex optimization problem, one can show that the optimum \tilde{m}_u values satisfy

$$\tilde{m}_u = \frac{\phi_u}{\sum_{u' \in \mathcal{U}^v} \phi_{u'}} \left(s^v - \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}^v} \min \left(\frac{l_b^{ge} \gamma_u}{c_u}, \frac{\gamma_u}{c_u} \right) \right).$$

This in turn coincides with the GREET allocation at the equilibrium, i.e., m_u^{ge} . Indeed, GREET first provides the share fraction needed by all users to satisfy the rate requirements and then distributes the remaining share proportional to ϕ_u , which is exactly what the above expression does. This implies that for the above \tilde{m}_u values it holds $U^v(\tilde{\mathbf{r}}^v) - U^v(\mathbf{r}^{ge,v}) = 0$ and hence slice v has no envy for the resources allocated to slice \tilde{v} at a GREET equilibrium.

Proof of Lemma 2

By construction, the GREET weight allocation algorithms allocates to each user the necessary weight to meet its minimum rate requirement.

Proof of Theorem 7

We show convergence by showing that Algorithm 1 is a contraction mapping. Specifically, consider two sequences slice-based weight allocations denoted $\mathbf{l}(n) : n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{l}}(n) : n \in \mathbb{N}$, where $\mathbf{l}(n) := (l_b^v(n) : v \in \mathcal{V}, b \in \mathcal{B})$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{l}}(n) := (\tilde{l}_b^v(n) : v \in \mathcal{V}, b \in \mathcal{B})$, corresponding to two initial weight allocations denoted $\mathbf{l}(0), \tilde{\mathbf{l}}(0)$ where at each step each slice performs its GREET weight allocation in response to that of the others in the previous step. We will establish that regardless the initial conditions, the following holds:

$$\max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| \leq \xi \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(n-1) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n-1)|$$

which suffices to establish convergence as long as $\xi < 1$.

We let $\mathbf{l}(n) := (l_b^v(n) : v \in \mathcal{V}, b \in \mathcal{B})$ denote the minimal slice weight allocations required by slice v at base station b based on the weight allocations in the previous round, i.e., $\mathbf{l}(n-1)$. Under Assumption 1, only Lines 4 and 5 in Algorithm 1 will be in effect, so

$$l_b^v(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v} l_b^{-v}(n-1), & l_b^{-v}(n-1) + f_b^v \leq 1, \\ f_b^v, & l_b^{-v}(n-1) + f_b^v > 1. \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Again under Assumption 1, the weight allocations for each slice and base station in response to the others $\mathbf{l}(n)$ is given by Line 21 in Algorithm 1, i.e., $l_b^v(n) = \tilde{l}_b^v(n) + \phi_b^v (s^v - \sum_{b' \in \mathcal{B}} \tilde{l}_{b'}^v(n))$ where $\phi_b^v = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_b^v} \phi_u$. Note that two particular cases are as follows: (i) if a slice v has solely inelastic users, we have $\phi_b^v = 0$ and thus $l_b^v(n) = \tilde{l}_b^v(n)$; and (ii) if a slice has solely elastic users, then $\tilde{l}_{b'}^v(n) = 0$ for all $b' \in \mathcal{B}$ and $l_b^v(n) = \phi_b^v s^v$. We define $\tilde{\mathbf{l}}(n)$ in the same way as $\mathbf{l}(n)$, based on $\tilde{\mathbf{l}}(n)$.

Next consider the difference between the two weight allocation sequences. Using the Triangle inequality, we obtain

$$|l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| \leq |l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| + \phi_b^v \sum_{b' \in \mathcal{B}} |l_{b'}^v(n) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^v(n)|.$$

Noting that (13) is a concave function with slope no greater than $\frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v}$ and again using the Triangle inequality, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} |l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| &\leq \frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v} |l_b^{-v}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_b^{-v}(n-1)| \\ &\leq \frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v} \sum_{v' \neq v} |l_{b'}^{v'}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^{v'}(n-1)|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, after one round of share updates, we have the following bound:

$$\begin{aligned} |l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| &\leq \frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v} \sum_{v' \neq v} |l_{b'}^{v'}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^{v'}(n-1)| \\ &+ \phi_b^v \sum_{b' \in \mathcal{B}} \frac{f_{b'}^v}{1-f_{b'}^v} \sum_{v' \neq v} |l_{b'}^{v'}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^{v'}(n-1)|. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

This in turn leads to the following bound on $\mathbf{l}(n) - \tilde{\mathbf{l}}(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(n) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n)| \\ &\leq \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \left\{ \frac{f_b^v}{1-f_b^v} \sum_{v' \neq v} |l_{b'}^{v'}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^{v'}(n-1)| \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \phi_b^v \sum_{b' \in \mathcal{B}} \frac{f_{b'}^v}{1-f_{b'}^v} \sum_{v' \neq v} |l_{b'}^{v'}(n-1) - \tilde{l}_{b'}^{v'}(n-1)| \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{2(|\mathcal{V}| - 1) f_{\max}}{1 - f_{\max}} \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} |l_b^v(n-1) - \tilde{l}_b^v(n-1)|, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the bound f_{\max} and that $\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \phi_b^v = 1$ unless slice v is inelastic in which case it equals 0. If (7) holds, we have that the weight allocation updates get closer. It follows by Proposition 1.1 in Chapter 3 of [40] that under simultaneous updates one has geometric convergence to the fixed point. Similarly, under round-robin updates, geometric convergence follows as a result of Proposition 1.4 in Chapter 3 of [40].

Proof of Theorem 8

This follows directly from the proof of Theorem 7 and Proposition 2.1 in Chapter 6 of [40].

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Vassilaras *et al.*, "The Algorithmic Aspects of Network Slicing," *IEEE Comm. Mag.*, vol. 55, no. 8, pp. 112–119, Aug. 2017.
- [2] G. Wang *et al.*, "Resource Allocation for Network Slices in 5G with Network Resource Pricing," in *Proc. IEEE GLOBECOM*, Dec. 2017.
- [3] V. Sciancalepore *et al.*, "Mobile Traffic Forecasting for Maximizing 5G Network resource Utilization," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, May 2017.
- [4] M. Leconte *et al.*, "A resource allocation framework for network slicing," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2018.
- [5] D. Bega *et al.*, "Deepcog: Cognitive network management in sliced 5g networks with deep learning," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2019.
- [6] —, "Optimising 5G Infrastructure Markets: The Business of Network Slicing," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, May 2017.
- [7] —, "Mobile Traffic Forecasting for Maximizing 5G Network resource Utilization," in *IEEE Tran. Mobile Comp.*, to appear.
- [8] X. Foukas *et al.*, "Orion: RAN slicing for a flexible and cost-effective multi-service mobile network architecture," in *Proc. ACM MOBICOM*, Oct. 2017.

- [9] I. Mahadevan and K. Sivalingam, "Quality of service architectures for wireless networks: Intserv and diffserv models," in *Proceedings Fourth International Symposium on Parallel Architectures, Algorithms, and Networks (I-SPAN'99)*, 1999, pp. 420–425.
- [10] J. Zheng *et al.*, "Statistical multiplexing and traffic shaping games for network slicing," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 2528–2541, Dec 2018.
- [11] P. Caballero *et al.*, "Multi-Tenant Radio Access Network Slicing: Statistical Multiplexing of Spatial Loads," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 3044–3058, Oct. 2017.
- [12] —, "Network Slicing Games: Enabling Customization in Multi-Tenant Mobile Networks," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 662–675, Apr. 2019.
- [13] —, "Network Slicing for Guaranteed Rate Services: Admission Control and Resource Allocation Games," *IEEE Tran. Wireless Comm.*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 6419–6432, Oct. 2018.
- [14] S. D'Oro *et al.*, "Low-complexity distributed radio access network slicing: Algorithms and experimental results," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 2815–2828, Dec. 2018.
- [15] 3GPP, "Self-Organizing Networks (SON) Policy Network Resource Model (NRM) Integration Reference Point (IRP); Information Service (IS)," TS 28.628, Jun. 2013.
- [16] R. Mahindra *et al.*, "Radio Access Network sharing in cellular networks," in *Proc. of IEEE ICNP*, Oct. 2013.
- [17] A. Gudipati, L. E. Li, and S. Katti, "RadioVisor: A Slicing Plane for Radio Access Networks," in *Proc. of HotSDN*, 2014.
- [18] V. Sciancalepore, V. Mancuso, A. Banchs, S. Zaks, and A. Capone, "Interference coordination strategies for content update dissemination in LTE-A," in *Proc. of IEEE INFOCOM*, May 2014.
- [19] Y. Du and G. de Veciana, "Wireless networks without edges: Dynamic radio resource clustering and user scheduling," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, April 2014, pp. 1–9.
- [20] S. D'Oro *et al.*, "The Slice Is Served: Enforcing Radio Access Network Slicing in Virtualized 5G Systems," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2019.
- [21] S. Mandelli *et al.*, "Satisfying Network Slicing Constraints via 5G MAC Scheduling," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2019.
- [22] A. Ksentini and N. Nikaein, "Toward enforcing network slicing on RAN: Flexibility and resources abstraction," *IEEE Comm. Mag.*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 102–108, Jun. 2017.
- [23] M. Richart *et al.*, "Resource slicing in virtual wireless networks: A survey," *IEEE Tran. Network Service Management*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 462–476, Sept 2016.
- [24] A. Asadi and V. Mancuso, "A survey on opportunistic scheduling in wireless communications," *IEEE Comm. Surveys and Tutorials*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1671–88, 2013.
- [25] S. Borst, N. Hegde, and A. Proutiere, "Mobility-Driven Scheduling in Wireless Networks," in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2009.
- [26] H. J. Kushner and P. A. Whiting, "Convergence of Proportional-Fair Sharing Algorithms Under General Conditions," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Comm.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1250–1259, Jul. 2004.
- [27] M. Kalil, A. Shami, and A. Al-Dweik, "QoS-Aware Power-Efficient Scheduler for LTE Uplink," *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comp.*, vol. 14, no. 8, pp. 1672–1685, Aug. 2015.
- [28] M. Mattess, C. Vecchiola, and R. Buyya, "Mobility-Driven Scheduling in Wireless Networks," in *Proc. IEEE HPC*, Sep. 2010.
- [29] Amazon, "EC2 Spot Instances," <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/spot/>.
- [30] Google Cloud, "Preemptible Virtual Machines," <https://cloud.google.com/preemptible-vms/>.
- [31] L. Zhang, "Proportional response dynamics in the Fisher market," *Theoretical Computer Science*, vol. 412, no. 24, pp. 2691–2698, May 2011.
- [32] S. Shenker, "Fundamental Design Issues for the Future Internet," *IEEE Journal of Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 1176–1188, Sep. 1995.
- [33] P. Hande, S. Zhang, and M. Chiang, "Distributed rate allocation for inelastic flows," *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1240–1253, Dec. 2007.
- [34] J. Mo and J. Walrand, "Fair end-to-end window-based congestion control," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 556–567, Oct. 2000.
- [35] M. Feldman, K. Lai, and L. Zhang, "The proportional-share allocation market for computational resources," *IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 8, p. 1075–1088, 2009.
- [36] F. P. Kelly, A. K. Maulloo, and D. Tan, "Rate control for communication networks: Shadow prices, proportional fairness, and stability," *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, vol. 49, pp. 237–252, Mar. 1998.
- [37] R. Johari and J. N. Tsitsiklis, "Efficiency Loss in a Network Resource Allocation Game," *Mathematics of Operations Research*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 407–435, Aug. 2004.
- [38] S. Yang and B. Hajek, "VCG-Kelly Mechanisms for Allocation of Divisible Goods: Adapting VCG Mechanisms to One-Dimensional Signals," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 1237–1243, Aug. 2007.
- [39] J. B. Rosen, "Existence and uniqueness of equilibrium points for concave n person games," *Econometrica*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 520–534, Jul. 1965.
- [40] D. Bertsekas and J. Tsitsiklis, *Parallel and distributed computation: numerical methods*. Prentice hall Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1989.
- [41] ITU-R, "Report ITU-R M.2135-1, Guidelines for evaluation of radio interface technologies for IMT-Advanced," Technical Report, Dec 2009.
- [42] Q. Ye *et al.*, "User Association for Load Balancing in Heterogeneous Cellular Networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Comm.*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 2706–2716, Jun. 2013.
- [43] 3GPP, "Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA); Physical layer procedures," TS 36.213, v12.5.0, Rel. 12, Mar. 2015.
- [44] E. Hyttia, P. Lassila, and J. Virtamo, "Spatial node distribution of the random waypoint mobility model with applications," *IEEE Trans. Mobile Computing*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 680–694, June 2006.
- [45] K. Lee *et al.*, "SLAW: self-similar least-action human walk," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 515–529, Apr. 2012.
- [46] A. K. Parekh and R. G. Gallager, "A generalized processor sharing approach to flow control in integrated services networks: The single-node case," *IEEE/ACM Trans. Networking*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 344–357, Jun. 2004.
- [47] S. Boyd and L. Vandenberghe, *Convex Optimization*. Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- [48] L. Li, M. Pal, and Y. R. Yang, "Proportional fairness in multi-rate wireless LANs," in *Proc. of IEEE INFOCOM*, Apr. 2008.

Jiaxiao Zheng received his M. Sc. and Ph.D. in electrical and computer engineering from The University of Texas at Austin in 2016 and 2019, respectively, under the supervision of Prof. de Veciana. He is currently associated with Applied ML department of Bytedance, focusing on hyper-scaled machine learning system for recommendation systems. His research interests lie in the design and optimization of ML system, resource allocation and sharing schemes in distributed systems, and modeling and optimization of human-in-the-loop systems.

Albert Banchs (M'04–SM'12) received his M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC-BarcelonaTech) in 1997 and 2002, respectively. He is currently a Full Professor with the University Carlos III of Madrid (UC3M), and has a double affiliation as Deputy Director (and acting director) of the IMDEA Networks institute. Before joining UC3M, he was at ICSI Berkeley in 1997, at Telefonica I+D in 1998, and at NEC Europe Ltd. from 1998 to 2003. He was an Academic Guest at ETHZ in 2012, a Visiting Professor at EPFL in

2015, 2013 and 2018 and a Fulbright scholar at University of Texas at Austin in 2019. His research focuses on the design, analysis, evaluation and implementation of wireless networking systems.

Gustavo de Veciana received his Ph.D. in electrical engineering from the U.C. Berkeley in 1993. He is currently a Cockrell Family Regents Chair in Engineering at the ECE Department in U.T. Austin. He served as the Director and Associate Director of the Wireless Networking and Communications Group (WNCG) from 2003–2007. His research focuses on the design, analysis and control networks, information theory and applied probability. Dr. de Veciana is currently an editor at large for the IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking. He was the recipient

of an NSF CAREER Award 1996 and a co-recipient of 7 best paper awards. In 2009 he was designated IEEE Fellow for his contributions to the analysis and design of communication networks. He currently serves on the board of trustees of IMDEA Networks Madrid.